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ETIOLOGY, PATHOGENESIS AND TREATMENT OF IRON DEFICIENCY ANEMIA

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Annotation. Iron deficiency anemia (IDA) is the most common form of anemia that occurs when there is a lack of iron in the body and is characterized by a decrease in the level of hemoglobin per unit volume of blood in combination with clinical signs of anemia [1]. Among all anemias, IDA is the most common and accounts for about 80% [2]. Iron deficiency affects almost half of the world's population (mostly women), the disease affects almost all age groups.

Keywords: IDA, iron, disease, therapy, DNA.

Iron is one of the main essential trace elements and is necessary for the normal functioning of many processes in the body. It is involved in redox processes, reactions of oxygen-dependent free radical oxidation and the antioxidant system, hematopoiesis, in supplying organs and tissues with oxygen, activation and inhibition of many enzymes and is part of hemoglobin, myoglobin and cytochromes. The most important metabolic processes in the body, such as DNA synthesis, gene regulation, cell proliferation and differentiation, steroid synthesis, proceed with the participation of iron [3,4]. That is why the deficiency of this particular trace element in the body affects many organs and systems and leads to serious consequences. Entering the body only about 10% of the amount of iron received is absorbed in the duodenum and in the upper sections of the small intestine. Up to 20% of iron is absorbed unchanged by the mucosal cell, only here the heme breaks down and iron is released. Iron is absorbed practically only in the diatomic form, since in the triatomic form, at a pH value of 5–7, it forms sparingly soluble hydroxides in the upper part of the small intestine, which cannot be absorbed. In accordance with the need of the body, a certain part of the absorbed iron is released into the bloodstream, and its remainder binds to a specific carrier molecule - apoferritin and accumulates in the form of ferritin. The accumulation and retention of iron in the body occurs with the help of transferrin, which serves as a transport reserve and forms the so-called latent binding capacity of iron. Almost all of the iron circulating in the blood plasma, as well as most of it in the extracellular fluid space, is tightly bound to transferrin. It transports iron to the main depots of the body, in particular, to the bone marrow, liver and spleen. After

endocytosis, iron is again transferred into the cells to apoferritin. Ferritin is a storage form that can be freely used by the body.

Methods. Through the process of denaturation of ferritin subgroups, hemosiderin is formed, in which the iron content is higher, but its release is much slower. Hemosiderin can be detected most often with an excess of iron in the body (for example, hemochromatosis); it accumulates, as a rule, in the liver, spleen, pancreas, skin and joints. The body is not able to excrete excess iron, and the regulation of its balance is carried out practically only in the process of resorption. Normally, in an adult, the absorption capacity is approximately 1 mg, which corresponds to almost 10% of iron intake per day. The body of an adult contains about 3–5 g of iron in bound form, and 70% of this amount is contained in hemoglobin. Therefore, the main share of iron is transferred to the bone marrow, where it is used for the synthesis of hemoglobin. After 100-120 days of life, erythrocytes in the liver, spleen and bone marrow break down, and the iron released in this case is again used to form hemoglobin and other compounds. The daily requirement for iron is about 1 mg, which in general can be provided through nutrition. With a lack of iron in the body, its depot is activated, which can lead to a relative compensation of the condition up to 2 years. It should also be remembered that only 10–20% of iron ingested with food is absorbed, so the amount of iron ingested should be increased by 5–10 times to cover the daily requirement [1]. The causes of IDA are varied. This may be due to a decrease in the intake of iron in the body due to malnutrition, for example, following certain diets [5] or vegetarianism. Due to impaired absorption of iron, which is mainly associated with the pathology of the gastrointestinal tract (resection of the small intestine, enteritis, malabsorption syndrome, Crohn's disease, lack of hydrochloric acid in gastric juice), due to an increased need for iron during hemodialysis or its increased consumption in puberty, during pregnancy, lactation and during intense physical exertion. Also, the development of IDA may be associated with increased loss of iron during bleeding from the gastrointestinal tract (tumors, diverticula, peptic ulcer, bleeding from hemorrhoids), with bleeding due to menorrhagia (heavy and prolonged menstruation, dysfunctional uterine bleeding, the presence of intrauterine contraceptives, gynecological and surgery, uterine fibroids and endometriosis) and from other organs, which is less common. Among the rarer causes of IDA, long-term donation and pathology of the valvular apparatus of the heart should be noted. Also, IDA often occurs when taking such drugs as anticoagulants, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, glucocorticosteroids [1,6]. In patients with IDA, the clinical picture shows symptoms characteristic of all anemias, such as general weakness, headaches, dizziness, shortness of breath when normal physical activity, tinnitus, flickering "flies" before the eyes, tachycardia, muscle weakness. Characteristic for IDA is a violation of taste sensations and

perception of smells, a decrease in appetite, a significant decrease in mental and physical performance. So-called "epithelial" symptoms are also noted: pallor, dryness and peeling of the skin, fragility and hair loss, stratification, transverse striation and fragility of nails, atrophy of the papillae of the tongue, angular stomatitis and dyspeptic disorders [7]. Pathology of the gastrointestinal tract (subatrophic and atrophic gastritis, colitis, lack of appetite, bloating, diarrhea, constipation), hepatobiliary system (formation of fatty hepatosis, biliary dyskinesia), cardiovascular system (anemic myocardial dystrophy, manifested by cardialgia, rhythm disturbances) is detected. etc., neurocirculatory dystonia) and the central nervous system (memory loss, ability to concentrate). Classification of IDA: • by form: alimentary, posthemorrhagic, due to increased iron consumption, due to resorptive iron deficiency, violation of its transport (atransferrinemia), etc. • by stages: prelatent iron deficiency - characterized by a decrease in trace element reserves, but without a decrease in iron consumption for erythropoiesis ; latent iron deficiency - when there is a complete depletion of trace element reserves in the depot, but there are still no signs of anemia development; Manifest iron deficiency (or IDA) that occurs with a decrease in the hemoglobin fund of iron and manifests itself as symptoms of anemia and hyposiderosis [8]. , severe anemia - Hb less than 70 g / l. To verify the diagnosis of IDA, in addition to the clinical picture, the results of laboratory tests are taken into account.

Results. After establishing the diagnosis and cause of IDA, the issue of prescribing therapy is decided. Currently, iron preparations are mainly used to treat iron deficiency conditions. First of all, it is necessary to try to influence the cause of iron deficiency. Treatment with iron preparations should be long-term, until stable normalization of red blood counts and replenishment of tissue iron deficiency. Also, do not forget that blood transfusion in IDA is indicated only for health reasons (anemic precoma and coma) [9]. In clinical practice, iron preparations are used orally or parenterally. Parenteral administration of drugs is indicated in the following situations: • in violation of iron absorption due to intestinal pathology (enteritis, malabsorption syndrome, resection of the small intestine, resection of the stomach and duodenum); • with exacerbation of gastric or duodenal ulcer; • with intolerance to iron preparations for oral administration, which does not allow continuing treatment (if a reduction in the dose of iron preparation and / or its replacement is ineffective). Iron preparations for parenteral administration are in trivalent form (as opposed to drugs for oral administration). The iron preparation Likferr 100® by Sotex is presented on the Russian pharmaceutical market. The drug is an iron [III] - sucrose hydroxide complex and is available in the form of a colloidal solution for intravenous administration. The introduction of 100 mg of the drug leads to an increase in hemoglobin by 2-3%. It should be noted that the hemoglobin level rises faster and more reliably than after drug therapy, containing divalent iron. The toxicity of the drug is very low, but it is

necessary to strictly observe the technique of administration of the drug and not exceed the required dose. The use of "Likferr 100®" is indicated in the following conditions: • iron deficiency conditions in patients with the need for rapid replenishment of iron; diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, in which oral iron preparations cannot be used. "Likferr 100®" is an effective drug for the complex treatment of anemic conditions in patients suffering from severe iron deficiency anemia against the background of chronic renal failure, including in patients who are on long-term hemodialysis, and during anticancer therapy. Anemia is observed in approximately 90% of patients, on program hemodialysis [10]. Its main causes are the lack of production of endogenous erythropoietin, a decrease in the life span of erythrocytes in uremia (hemolysis), and, finally, iron deficiency, which has multiple genesis [11]. Thus, it has been shown that the treatment of anemia in patients with end-stage chronic renal failure who are on permanent hemodialysis not only improves the quality of life of patients, but also directly affects mortality. generally changed the idea of the adequacy of renal replacement therapy. The company "Sotex" also produces a hemopoiesis stimulator "Eralfon®" (epoetin alfa). The drug is available as a solution for intravenous and subcutaneous injection in syringes from 0, 3 to 1.0 ml. The syringe contains from 1000 to 40,000 IU of the active substance - epoetin alfa. Epoetin alfa is a glycoprotein that specifically stimulates erythropoiesis, activates the cytolysis and maturation of erythrocytes from erythrocyte progenitor cells. Recombinant epoetin alfa is synthesized in mammalian cells into which the gene encoding human erythropoietin is inserted. In its composition, biological and immunological properties, epoetin alfa is identical to natural human erythropoietin. The introduction of epoetin alfa leads to an increase in hemoglobin and hematocrit levels, an improvement in blood supply to tissues and heart function. The most pronounced effect of the use of epoetin alfa is observed in anemia caused by chronic renal failure. that it reduces the concentration of cyclosporine due to an increase in the degree of its binding to red blood cells (it may be necessary to adjust the dose of cyclosporine). Also, the drug is pharmaceutically incompatible with solutions of other drugs. During treatment with recombinant human erythropoietins, it is necessary to monitor blood pressure and indicators of platelet count, hematocrit and ferritin levels. It is important to remember that Eralfon® does not replace blood transfusion in the treatment of anemia, but reduces the need for its repeated use. In patients with controlled arterial hypertension or a history of thrombotic complications, an increase in the dose of antihypertensive drugs and / or anticoagulants, respectively, may be required. When administered to patients with hepatic insufficiency, it is possible to slow down the metabolism of epoetin alfa and a pronounced increase in erythropoiesis. The possibility that a preoperative increase in hemoglobin levels may be a predisposing factor to the development of thrombotic complications should be considered. Before elective surgery, patients

should receive adequate prophylactic antiplatelet therapy. In the pre- and postoperative period, the drug is not recommended for patients with an initial hemoglobin level of more than 150 g / l. In patients with chronic renal failure, it is necessary to control the level of electrolytes in the blood serum. Prior to the start of treatment, it is necessary to assess the iron stores (focusing on the level of ferritin) in the body and, if it is deficient, carry out a correction.

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